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Landscape and birds diversity in the Kayabi and Apiaká indigenous territories in the Amazon rainforest

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a photographic summary of studies carried out in June 2011 in Kayabi and Apiaká indigenous territories, located on the margin of the Teles Pires River, between the states of Mato Grosso and Pará, in the Brazilian Amazon. A scientific expedition was carried out to analyze the environmental impacts of a project in the region and more specifically the possible interferences in the life of the indigenous inhabitants of the region and live in harmony with the environment. The photos show some structures of indigenous villages, the Teles Pires River, the riparian forest where studies were carried out and some of the bird species registered.

Keywords: Amazon rainforest, fauna, Brazil, ecology, indigenous, Teles Pires River

INTRODUCTION

The Amazon Rainforest is one of the principal Brazilian biomes and is formed by dense tropical forests and associated ecosystems, and represents over half of the planet's remaining rainforests, and comprises the largest and most biodiverse tract of tropical rainforest in the world. An immense number of bird species live in the Amazon rainforest, with over 1,300 species, which accounts for one-third of all bird species in the world. Many scientific researches carried out in the Amazon demonstrate its richness in avifauna [1-18].

Among the many factors thought to contribute to the high bird species richness in the Neotropics is the high diversity of habitat and microhabitat types, some of which are unique to tropical regions [19, 20]. The increase in structural complexity of the vegetation on various vertical levels makes new forms of occupancy of the environment possible [21]. The increase in the number of bird species is principally due to the increase of both the new food guilds and the number of species in the existing guilds [22].

The Teles Pires River (Photos 1-10, 50-52) rises in central Mato Grosso State and flows north northwestward, where it joins the Juruena River to form the Tapajós River, a major tributary of the Amazon River. For 200 miles (320 km) the Teles Pires marks part of the state boundary between Pará and Mato Grosso states. Its 870-mile (1,400-km) course is frequently interrupted by waterfalls and rapids.

The studies were carried out in Kayabi and Apiaká Indigenous Territories, in June 2011. The Apiaká territory studied is located in the Mato Grosso State, Southern Brazilian Amazon Rainforest, at the left edge of Teles Pires River, in the Apiacás municipal district. It lies between 07°39'S to 08°32'S latitude and 57°50'W to 58°21'W longitude, covering an area of 9.820 km². The Kayabi territory studied is located between the states Pará and Mato Grosso, covering part of the municipalities Jacareacanga (Southwest of the Pará) and Apiacás (North of the Mato Grosso), on the edge of the Teles Pires River. It lies between 07°54'S to 09°13'S latitude and 56°39'W to 57°54'W longitude, covering an area of about 1.053.000 km² (Figure 1).

The Ciliary Forest that follows the Teles Pires River, where bird studies were conducted, is a very well-preserved forest (Photos 11-17, 49, 53). The Kayabi and Apiaká villages are located on the edge of this river (Photos 18, 31, 38). It is in the demarcated territories of the indigenous Kayabi and Apiaká, that forests are best conserved. Unfortunately, these lands that

should be protected, suffer permanent pressure from gold digging, invasions, clandestine occupation, and the advancement of pasture areas for cattle breeding with river poisoning and devastation of the surrounding natural forests.

Figure 1. Location of the Kururuzinho village (Kayabi indigenous territory) and Mayrowi village (Apiaká indigenous territory), where the studies were carried out. These indigenous villages are located between the states of Mato Grosso and Pará, on the banks of the Teles Pires River. They are close to the great Munduruku indigenous territory.

The indigenous people live in balance with the environment where in which they live. They use natural resources to build their homes, such as timber for the structure and palm leaves to cover them (Photos 19-23, 34-44). Firewood is the only source of energy for the Kayabi and Apiaká, and is really important for indigenous to prepare the food (Photos 24, 25). The Kayabi and Apiaká economic system is characterized by a combination of the activities of gathering, hunting, fishing, and agriculture. They mainly grow cassava and corn, which are the basis of their food (Photos 26, 27, 45-47).

The access to the main Kayabi village (called Kururuzinho) was by boat across the Teles Pires River, from a port located 60 km of Alta Floresta, which is the main city in the studied region with an airport. It took about 140 km to travel across the Teles Pires River.

The distance between the Kururuzinho village and the Mayrowi village, in Apiaká territory, is about 150 km along the Teles Pires River. The trip on the Teles Pires River is not viable not only due to the distance, but also the course is frequently interrupted by waterfalls and rapids, which makes the trip quite dangerous and long. So, this route was made by single engine plane, as well as the return to Alta Floresta (Photos 30, 54). The flights we performed were important for the best view of the Teles Pires River and the forest (Photos 32-37, 55).

The knowledge of the abundance of the fauna among the Kayabi and Apiaká is surprising not only for the great number of birds species identified for the indigenous, but also in the high degree of these people's observation, to the point of they indicate taxonomics details that individualize species taxonomically similar. They have mentioned 165 different species of birds [23] and 36 different species of mammals [24].

Some of these animals have been domesticated and are used as pets (Photos 28, 48), and the name given to these animals is “xerimbabo”, which in the Tupi language (Brazilian indigenous language). Among the registered bird species, 45 are presented through photographs (Photos 56-100). A broader conception of non-formal ornithological knowledge of different societies may help formal observers to value local or popular knowledge and relativize the utilitarian and nominal view [25].

All photos presented in this report were realized by Fabio Rossano Dario, using a digital photo camera Canon PowerShot SX30 IS. The birds’ photos are presented in taxonomic order according to the new systematic list of CBRO [26].

CONCLUSIONS

The Amazon rainforest and its rivers host an extraordinary variety of species, some endemic, others endangered, and many of which are still unknown. It is considered one of the areas on the planet with the most number of bird species. This biodiversity is very important globally, because as the largest biodiversity reserve in the world, this biome has a big amount of growing stock and carbon, and a wide diversity of non-wood forest products. However, this region has experienced a continuing increase in anthropogenic pressures, mainly from deforestation, which implies a strong concern for the conservation of the biota of this region, and the security of indigenous communities who live in it.

The Kayabi and Apiaká people have a rich culture and are among the most gentle and cultured people that I have ever known in my life. They received the research team with great affection and taught us many things about the environment in which they live. They respect the rivers, the forest and all the living beings that live in it (Photo 29).

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Photo 1. Teles Pires River. Detail of boat used in the expedition.

Photo 2. Teles Pires River.

Photo 3. Teles Pires River.

Photo 4. Natural sand beach on the Teles Pires River.

Photo 5. Beach of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 6. Butterflies feeding on minerals on the beaches of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 7. The Teles Pires River basin is a speciose region for butterflies.

Photo 8. Teles Pires River.

Photo 9. Sunset at Teles Pires River.

Photo 10. Sunset at Teles Pires River.

Photo 11. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 12. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 13. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 14. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 15. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 16. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 17. Riparian forest of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 18. Detail of Kayabi village located on the edge of a tributary of the Teles Pires River.

Photo 19. Kayabi village house made of wood, clay and babassu palm leaf (*Attalea speciosa*) for coverage.

Photo 20. Kayabi village house made of wood and covered with babassu palm leaves.

Photo 21. Kayabi village house made of wood and covered with babassu palm leaves.

Photo 22. Detail of the Kayabi house roof made of wood and babassu palm leaves.

Photo 23. Detail of the Kayabi house roof made of wood and babassu palm leaves.

Photo 24. Firewood is the only source of energy for the Kayabi and Apiaká.

Photo 25. Firewood is important for indigenous people in preparing food.

Photo 26. Corn is a staple food grown by brazilian indigenous.

Photo 27. Detail for the cultivation of spices and medicinal herbs in Kayabi village.

Photo 28. Detail of parrot (*Amazona aestiva*) used by indigenous people as a pet.

Photo 29. In the company of a dear friend Kayabi.

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Photo 35. Aerial view of the Amazon Rainforest.

Photo 36. Aerial view of the Amazon Rainforest.

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Photo 40. Apiaká village house made of wood and covered with babassu palm leaves.

Photo 41. Apiaká village house made of wood and covered with babassu palm leaves.

Photo 42. Apiaká village house made of wood and covered with babassu palm leaves.

Photo 43. Detail of the Apiaká house roof made of wood and babassu palm leaves.

Photo 44. Detail of the Apiaká house roof made of wood and babassu palm leaves.

Photo 45. Detail for the cultivation of spices and medicinal herbs in Mayrowi village, Apiaká territory.

Photo 46. Detail of banana plantation in Mayrowi village, Apiaká territory.

Photo 47. Manioc (*Manihot esculenta*) is a root crop that is cultivated by many indigenous groups in Amazonia.

Photo 48. Detail of baby tapir (*Tapirus terrestris*) used by indigenous people as a pet.

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Photo 50. Teles Pires River.

Photo 51. Teles Pires River.

Photo 52. Teles Pires River. Detail of boat used in the expedition.

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Photo 57. *Butorides striata*, Ardeidae (socozinho; Striated Heron).

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